
Predict the value at risk in an investment portfolio using Monte Carlo simulation

(A case study)

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to use the Monte Carlo simulation model to predict the risk value of the Syrian Islamic International Bank's investment portfolio to assess the risks it may face and make investment decisions based on careful risk and return analysis. For this purpose, data on the Bank's finance portfolio was collected in 2024, and the expected losses in this portfolio were then applied to the Monte Carlo simulation model to predict the value at risk using the R-Studio program. Thus, strategic decision-making information is provided to identify and deal effectively with credit risks. The results showed that the maximum future loss to the investment portfolio would exceed the total projected losses for individual portfolio-formed loans. The researcher recommended that the Syrian Islamic International Bank reduce the amount of funding in the coming period to reduce the value at risk in the future. In addition, the study emphasized the importance of continuously following the development of the investment portfolio to ensure continuous improvements in risk assessment. It also stressed the need to strengthen the Bank's analytical capabilities and to employ other tools to support more effective forecasting and risk management and to repricing of loans according to the new tender.

Keywords

Monte Carlo Simulation, Value at Risk, KMV Model, Expected Loss, Default Threshold.

1 . Introduction:

Banks operate under changing economic conditions that carry many risks. Perhaps the most important challenges facing banks are those related to credit granted to others, with which the possibility of exposure to many risks, including credit risks, necessitates the management of the bank to look for new ways and mechanisms to face those risks and reduce them to maintain the optimal return, where the prediction of credit risk in the loan portfolio is one of the main challenges faced by these banks, where this prediction allows estimating the value at risk in the event of default.

Researchers in this field have used many analytical models and statistical techniques to estimate the value at risk, including Monte Carlo simulation by generating a wide range

of possible outcomes that simulate the behavior of the portfolio over a specified period and determine the probability of default in that portfolio to reach the maximum possible loss to be experienced during a given period. Thus providing information for strategic decision-making to identify and deal with credit risks effectively contributes to achieving financial stability and achieving the desired financial goals.

This study aims to employ Monte Carlo simulation models to predict the value at risk in an investment portfolio that plays a prominent role in the success or failure of financing, and the importance of this study lies in two dimensions: First, the definition of the concept of credit risk and its measurement mechanism. Second, review the methods of estimating the value at risk and using them in both managing credit risk on the one hand and reducing portfolio risk on the other, thus contributing to improving risk management, enhancing financial stability in addition to ensuring the bank's ability to deal with economic fluctuations and unexpected events better.

Therefore, the importance of this study stems in theory from providing a strong and accurate analytical tool to help banks assess risk and determine the maximum loss incurred by the investment portfolio to make the right decisions related to granting credit, that is, help in enhancing the ability to manage risk and make investment decisions at a high level of accuracy and scientific analysis. In practical terms, the study is important in employing Monte Carlo simulation models for the prediction of value at risk, as Monte Carlo simulation enables challenges related to the complexity of traditional statistical models to be overcome.

This study is divided into six main sections, the second section reviews the theoretical background and the development of hypotheses. While the third section addresses the concept of credit risk and its measurement methods. In the fourth section Monte Carlo simulation techniques are presented, along with how they can be employed to predict the value at risk (VAR) for a portfolio over a specific time period. The fifth section explains the methodology and tests the research hypothesis, in addition to presenting the main experimental results. The study concludes in the sixth section with findings and recommendations.

2-Theoretical.background.and.hypothesis.development:

Banks need to assess the expected maximum loss and hence the concept of value at risk, which is defined (Qandouz 2020; Alexander, 2003; Harmantzis, 2005; Manganell, 2001) as a statistical measure used to measure portfolio risk, identify potential losses in portfolio value as a result of unfavorable changes in the daily market environment, simply estimating the value that a portfolio can lose in adverse market conditions over a specified period and at a specified level of confidence. Studies that predict value at risk in an investment portfolio can be divided into three main streams: The classical current focuses on applying traditional financial theories such as investment theory and traditional financial analysis in estimating value at risk. Behavioral current This current focuses on the psychological and behavioral factors that influence financial decision-making and the estimation of value at risk, and the modern current combines the previous two trends, namely, combining traditional theories and behavioral factors, with a focus on the application of modern technology and innovations in the estimation of

value at risk. Many theories test the parameters of the practical analysis of risk and return, such as the modern Portfolio Theory proposed by Markowitz (1952) and developed by William Sharpe in 1964 in collaboration with John Lintner to the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) (Fama & French, 2004). Which is an important tool for estimating the return of financial assets based on the risks involved. After making some important adjustments in the seventies, Fama proposed the effective market hypothesis, which assumes that asset prices reflect all available information and cannot predict its volatility Fama (1991) ,Amos Tversky & Daniel Kahneman advocated the use of the prospect theory, This theory was formulated in 1979 and further developed in 1992 describes how individuals choose between probabilistic alternatives where there is risk and the probability of different unknown outcomes.(Rubin & Estevez & Chen, 2024). The prediction of value at risk was subject to many adjustments until the modern-day pioneer Richard Thaler (1988), who contributed significantly to the development of understanding about how psychological and behavioral factors influence financial decision-making and value appreciation at risk. Thus, it has indirectly contributed to improving methods of forecasting value at risk by promoting a comprehensive understanding of how psychological and social factors interact with financial decision-making processes, and several analytical tools have been used to predict value at risk such as the analytical method (Parametric VAR) and Historical Simulation Method (Danielsson et al., 1997) compared the semi-parametric method to historical simulation and J. P. Morgan's risk measurement technique on the portfolio. For predictions of the worst outcomes with low probability, the analysis of risk metrics predicts less than the value at risk, while historical simulations predict too much. Monte Carlo Simulation has been introduced to facilitate successful planning for strong results as the Monte Carlo simulation of projects provides a way to deal with uncertainty Antony (2011), whereas Gunay (2017) used the unnatural distributions model (fat-tailed Distributions) by analyzing various VAR value models used to measure the risk of passive investment. Using different methods and simplified facts of financial time series he measured the passive investment of a single asset and virtual portfolio through traditional VAR models (VAR Parametric, Historical VAR, Historical VAR Simulation, and VAR Monte Carlo Simulation).

3. The concept and measurement of credit risk:

"The risk is a problem (situation, event, etc.) Which has not yet appeared, but may occur in the future" Platona (2014) Credit risk is defined as risk arising from an inability to pay or reschedule payments and is events related to changes in the credit quality of the borrower (credit migration) Oorato (2005), and is related to unforeseen loss, this will result in an economic loss to Schroeck (2002), including a counterparty loss. To cover credit risk, we must calculate portfolio losses, including expected losses and unexpected losses, and the coverage of actual credit losses may depend (in some cases) on collateral, as it can be liquidated to cover some losses, Banks (2003). "The bank may use the event as a lever to renegotiate terms" Fight (2004)"Default probabilities impact

the market value of the financial contract through ratings and discounting credit spreads"(Stagars & kizidis, 2016)

In these cases, banks simulate the evolution of market risk and credit risk factors to achieve compatibility with changes that may occur, by creating models or systems that rely on available data and simulate credit market developments. This simulation aims to understand how credit costs are determined according to value-at-risk estimates and market-related variables, as well as their impact on banks' credit risk.

Many organizations use simulation models to predict value at risk, estimate potential risks, and evaluate their impact on their credit portfolios. These models rely on the analysis of historical data and the application of statistical and financial models to create realistic scenarios of market developments and analyze their potential impact on credit portfolios.

3.1. losses arising from credit risk:

A. Expected Loss (EL):

The approved entry for losses adopted by Basel II defines *expected losses (El) as losses that can and cannot occur*.. The expected loss is determined by the average value of the probability distribution of future losses, in practice the expected loss is estimated in advance by the lender, which makes it hedge the risk by adding an appropriate price difference to the required profit rate on the loan, and therefore in the event of default of the borrower. The lender will receive the expected net return Gerhard (2002).

Estimating the expected loss when making a loan requires three criteria:

- **Exposure at Default (EAD):** A random variable represented by current exposure in addition to the potential variation in loan size that may take from now to a potential date when it will default, the amount of loss exposure can be difficult to estimate. Then the decision maker can use the Monte Carlo Simulation technique to estimate the amount of loss exposure Gerhard (2002).
- **Probability of The Default (PD):** The probability of failure of the borrower (in repayment) before the end of the specified period (the estimated horizon is usually one year), and the concept of probability of default differs from the concept of credit score, which usually expresses an institutional or statistical classification of the borrower's reliability in paying debts. The credit score can be positive or negative while the probability of default falls between (0 and 1) so one of the main challenges we face is how to convert the credit score to the probability of default (Joseph, 2013; Gerhard, 2002).
- **Loss Given Event Defaulted (LGD):** Any percentage of loss exposure that the bank expects to be able to recover (e.g. by taking over collateral or claiming collateral...) It is equal to $LGD = 1 - RR$. One minus the expected Recovery Rate (RR) upon exposure to the loss Resti (2007), and can take a value between 0% and 100%

We conclude that the value of expected losses Nawlo (2022) can be calculated as follows:

$$EL = \mathbb{E} (\widetilde{L}_n) \cdot EAD \cdot PD \cdot LGD \dots\dots(1)$$

$$EL_P = \mathbb{E} (\widetilde{L}_n) = \sum_{i=1}^N EAD_i \cdot PD_i \cdot LGD_i \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

The expected loss of the credit portfolio is generated by the sum of the expected losses of the assets EBF (2016).

EAD_i: Credit exposure upon default of the borrower(i)

PD_i: Borrower's probability of default (i)

EAD_i: Loss of exposure to the borrower (i)

H0: The maximum expected loss of the investment portfolio at a 99% confidence level will not exceed the total projected losses of individual loans in this portfolio at present, assuming no change in the composition of the portfolio.

B. Unexpected Loss (UL): is defined as loss arising from unexpected deviations in credit loss levels. They are potential losses that is, they exist but are not enabled /possible for any risk factor to do/both are calculated using a 12-month time horizon.

Table 1. summarizes the two types of losses that the investment portfolio is exposed to (Gerhard,2002., EBF,2016)

Table1. Types of losses that an investment portfolio is exposed to

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Probable financial loss over a 12-month time horizon at a specified confidence level.	(EL) Expected Loss
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Potential financial loss over a 12-month time horizon at a specified confidence level.	Un Expected Loss (UL)

3.2. Credit risk Measurement methods: There are several credit risk measurement techniques available to measure the risk of default to a bank using market information, including distance to default and bond prices practically market-based indicators are more accurate than accounting indicators and more useful in predicting bank failure.

A. Creditrisk+™ Model: Known as the actuarial credit model, which Credit Suisse Financial Products worked on in 1997 and was an approach derived from the insurance business and applied to credit risk Bessis(2015) as it relied on tools used in the mathematics of insurance (actuarial mathematics) and specifies that credit losses stem from two main variables: 1. Repetition of the event.2 - The amount to be paid when the event occurs (severity of loss). Losses depend on the frequency of default events and the rate of loss in case of default, and on this measurement, it is possible to use insurance-derived models to estimate credit losses.

Repayment risk and recovery risk will be treated as inevitable and therefore neither default nor recovery risk can be estimated. CreditRisk+™ Model (unlike structural models) does not seek to explain the cause of default; on the contrary, it assumes that debtors default odds and repayment rates for their loans have already been estimated by other tools (such as the bank's internal rating system: it is a system used by banks and financial institutions to classify credit risk for current and potential bank customers or studies produced by rating agencies (as Standard & poor's and Moody's and Fitch Ratings).

B. Merton Model: This most common credit risk measurement model assesses the probability of a company defaulting at a given time and, based on Merton's approach, the borrower defaults when the market value of its assets falls below the book value of its obligations O'Kane (2006). to estimate the probability of default, subtract the face value of the company's debt from the estimated market value of the company and divide the difference by the estimated volatility of the company, resulting in a/ Z-score/ often referred to as the default distance degree (DD), and the Merton model assumes that the

company's equity is equivalent to the option to purchase the company's assets. Since shareholders are the remaining claimants to the assets of the company after all obligations have been fulfilled. Merton's model is based on an important assumption that the total market value of a company's underlying assets follows a geometric Brownian movement.

$$dV_A = \mu V_A dt + \sigma_A V_A dW \dots (3)$$

Where V_A : The value of a company's assets, μ Is the expected immediate periodic rate of σ_A return on an asset, the immediate standard deviation of the rate of return on an asset, or the fluctuation of An asset dW ¹ is the standard winner process.

- **Calculation of the probability of Default in Banking:** To estimate the probability of default, the Merton model proposes to view the value of the borrowing company's equity as a purchase option relative to assets, with the Merton method based on the following idea: When a loan is due or its interest if the borrowed company's assets are less than the value of its liabilities. It will not be able to repay this loan and therefore will default in this case the value of equity subs equity will fall to zero, and if the value of its assets V_A is greater than the value of its liabilities then it will be able to repay the loans and the market value of the equity of the company will equal the difference between the value of its assets and the value of its liabilities. The present market value of a stock can be expanded V_E , assuming that the value of the company's assets at the moment t is the logarithm of the normal distribution, and that the loans the company has received are insured, the Merton model shows that using the Black and Scholes formula for purchase options the initial price of its equity is Gerhard (2002):

$$V_E = V_A N(d_1) - X e^{-rT} N(d_2) \dots (4)$$

$$d_1 = \frac{\ln(\frac{V_A}{X}) + (r + 0.5 \sigma_A^2)T}{\sigma_A \sqrt{T}} \dots (5)$$

$$d_2 = d_1 - \sigma_A \sqrt{T} \dots (6)$$

$$d_2 = \frac{\ln(\frac{V_A}{X}) + (r + 0.5 \sigma_A^2)T}{\sigma_A \sqrt{T}} = d_1 - \sigma_A \sqrt{T} \dots (7)$$

Where r : Is the risk-free interest rate, σ_A Is the instantaneous standard deviation of the rate of return on the value of an asset (volatility of assets) and N is the cumulative rate of the standard normal distribution density function and x is the value of a company's liabilities.

¹ The standard Wiener process is a continuous and unpredictable process, in which the instantaneous rate of return on an asset changes randomly and continuously. The standard deviation of the standard Wiener process is a measure of the volatility or variations in the value of an asset over time. The higher the standard deviation, the greater the degree of volatility or fluctuation in the value of the asset.

- **Distance-to-default Probability:** is the distance between a company's expected asset value in the horizontal analysis and the default point, the calculation of the probability dimension DD requires two equations Resti (2007): The first is the equation that V_E States that the value of a company's equity is a function of the value of the company, the second relates to the volatility of the company.

$$DD_t = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{V_{A,t}}{x_t}\right) + \left(\mu - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_A^2\right)T}{\sigma_A\sqrt{T}} \dots\dots(8)$$

V_A : value of assets, σ_A : volatility of assets x_t : total liabilities, T: time period .
Therefore, is calculated *the* probability of default with the following relationship:
PD= N(-DD)

PD: the probability of default N: cumulative probability distribution

C. KMV Model: this model was developed by Moody's KMV in 1993 where, based on a sample of several hundred companies, KMV noted that companies are more likely to default when their asset values reach a certain critical level somewhere in between total value obligations and the value of short-term obligations. KMV implements an additional step; (Saunders 2010; Zieliński, 2009) that refers *to the* critical default threshold as the default point /default threshold/, for the KMV model the default point is rounded (DPT) approximately by the sum of all short term debt (STD) and half of the long-term liabilities:(TD)

$$DPT = STD + 0.5LTD \dots\dots(9)$$

The KMV approach calculates the known Distance to Default(DD) Kimber (2004) index is defined as the distance between a company's projected asset value in the horizontal analysis and the default point that is settled by the standard deviation of future asset returns. The absolute probability of default DD' Is expressed (in expected asset percentages) as the distance between the expected asset and the default point (DPT).

$$DD' = \ln\left(\frac{A_0}{DPT}\right) + \left(\mu_A - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_A^2\right)T \dots\dots(10)$$

$$DD = \frac{E(A_T) - DPT}{\sigma} \dots\dots(11)$$

In the KMV model, μ_A it is no longer risk-free but the expected rate of return of the company's assets and **DPT** is the point of default rather than debt (face value of debt), the expected growth of the asset is equal $\left(\mu_A - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_A^2\right)$ instead of μ_A , Whereas the rate of return is normally distributed as the future value of the investment (or actual return of the return). μ_A logarithmic distribution, which is the rate of deviation (expected rate of return). $\ln\left(\frac{S_T}{S}\right) \sim N\left(\left(\mu_A - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_A^2\right)\sigma_A\sqrt{T}\right)$ By dividing the absolute value DD' With the volatility of the asset (according to /T/period, usually one year) we can calculate DD in relative terms as a multiplier of the standard deviation.

$$DD = d_2 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{A_0}{DPT}\right) + \left(\mu_A - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_A^2\right)T}{\sigma_A\sqrt{T}} \dots\dots(12)$$

Figure 1. Distribution of the value of the company's assets when the loan is due Zieliński (2009).

DD Similar to d_2 (with the replacement of r with μ_A and x_t with DPT) Similarity is the result of the relationship between risk-free probability and actual probability, the actual probability is the deviation of the expected return of an asset from the desired return, while the risk-free probability is the risk-free rate. Considering the value of assets normally distributed after a period of T /often a year/ according to the definition of default (the value of the company's assets is less than DPT) Zieliński (2009). we can estimate the probability of default using the equation:

$$PD = 1 - N(d_2) = V(-DD) \dots (13)$$

D. One-Factor Model: In this model, the probability of default in an investment portfolio depends on one factor, *the value of assets* is an important factor that is used to assess the strength of financial resources and the ability to meet financial obligations in the future considering that there is a standard normal random variable $\tilde{r}_i$ That represents the condition of future debtors.² We will denote the critical threshold for borrower i by C_i , And say that borrower i is in default in the future Leeuwaarden (2011). if: $C_i < \tilde{r}_i$

$$PD_i = \mathbb{P}(C_i < \tilde{r}_i) \dots (14)$$

BY dividing the variable $\tilde{r}_i$ Two parts are called the composite factor, which generally deals with external influences on the borrower, and these effects cannot be directly controlled and affect the economic state of the borrower (such as oil prices, political situation, etc.). The Idiosyncratic part is the borrower's part and refers to the unique effects on the borrower's performance and related to its features and modus operandi. These effects can include internal factors such as management strategies and the ability of the company to adapt to changes in the market. We will denote the comprehensiveness factor by $Z \sim N(0,1)$ and the factor specific to borrower i by y_i

² The random variable $\tilde{r}_i$ is denoted as follows: Given that the current value of the company's assets is denoted by $A_0^{(i)}$ while the future value of the assets at time T is $A_T^{(i)}$ assume that $A_0^{(i)}$ and $A_T^{(i)}$ follow the lognormal distribution $\tilde{r}_i = \text{Log}(A_T^{(i)}/A_0^{(i)})$ then the value of $\tilde{r}_i$ is r_i standard or normative meaning $\tilde{r}_i = (r_i \mathbb{E}|\tilde{r}_i|/\sqrt{\text{Var}|\tilde{r}_i|}) \sim N(0,1)$ where the normative values refer to fixed values used as a reference point for comparison.

$\sim N(0,1)$ Let us assume that Z, Y_i If it is independent, then the correlation factor will be $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$.

$\tilde{r}_1 \leftarrow \sqrt{P} \cdot Z + \sqrt{1 - P} \cdot Y_1$ This correlation factor for the model determines the *expected* loss of a single borrower we can assume that each loan comprises several variables Leeuwarden (2011):

$$EL = EAD \cdot LGD \cdot I_{(D)} \dots (15)$$

$$I_{(D)} \sim \text{Bin}(1, PD) \dots (16)$$

Figure 2. Distribution of investment portfolio loss variables. Leeuwarden, (2011).

Assuming that we have an investment portfolio of n debtors, each debtor in the portfolio has a risk score associated with it to be marked with the symbol i , and therefore the investment portfolio risk can be determined by the total risk associated with each debtor that makes up this portfolio using the following relationship:

$$\tilde{L}_n := \sum_{i=0}^n EAD_i \cdot LGD_i \cdot I_{(D_i)} \dots (17)$$

$$I_{(D_i)} \sim \text{Bin}(1, PD_i) \dots (18)$$

Where these variables represent the sum of all the individual variables of loss and therefore the distribution $\tilde{L}_n$, Includes all the information related to the credit risk in the portfolio through the following variables Resti (2007):

- EL: Expected Loss $EL := \tilde{L}_n$
- UL: Unexpected loss can be defined as the standard deviation of a portfolio loss

$UL = \sqrt{\text{Var}[\tilde{L}_n]}$ Unexpected loss captures deviations away from the expected value of the loss that exceeds expectations.

- Var: Value at risk it means determining the expected value of the risk based on the specified level of confidence. Nawlo (2022) :

$$VaR_\alpha = \inf \{x \geq 0: \mathbb{P}(\tilde{L}_n \leq x) \geq \alpha\} \text{ where } \alpha(0,1)$$

- EC Economic capital $EC_\alpha = VaR_\alpha - EL$ This is called capital cushion the risk value can be used as a method of selecting the appropriate capital cushion Gerhard (2002), for example, if the capital cushion is chosen by the amount of the one-year risk value at the level of α , the capital cushion is expected to be sufficient at) $100 \cdot (1 - \alpha) \%$ of years. So if the value of $\alpha = 0.998$, the portfolio loss is expected to exceed the capital cushion only twice in 1000 years Bessis (2015) What makes

distribution analysis $\widetilde{L}_n$ Interesting is that variables $I_{(D_i)}$ Are usually related to each other.

4. Simulation of portfolio risk:

Monte Carlo simulation: The name of this method dates back to the French city of Monaco, where the Monte Carlo simulation opened the door to solving complex problems Mun (2006) where the Monte Carlo simulation generates random numbers Barrailler (2014) useful in prediction and statistical inference, where real data is collected for three funding applicants. A random number generator is then used to generate hundreds or perhaps tens of thousands of hypothetical changes to predict the value at risk, the Monte Carlo simulation imposes the risk structure that Pallotta (2000) is supposed to look at.

Monte Carlo simulation of portfolio risk is carried out according to scientific studies using two basic types of simulation through which the distribution of portfolio losses is modeled:

1- Simulation of Times To Default: along the lines of the “reduced form” model of default (Bessis,2015; Roszbach,2003) This enables analysts to assess potential risks in the portfolio and make smarter investment decisions.

2- Simulations of dependent default event with the asset model: This technique is used by Moody's KMV Model and Credit risk+TM Based on the "structural default model", where default under this model occurs when the value of the assets is lower or equal to the threshold corresponding to the probability of default for each borrower. Simulations of default events are generated using a standardized model of asset value, where all factors affecting the general borrower are included to determine its probability of default this model assumes that the value of the asset follows the normal distribution and therefore the default point is a function of the probability of default for each borrower Bessis (2015). Then default occurs when the value of the assets owned by the borrower is less or equal to a certain level of probability of default, and when simulation is performed within the investment portfolio the number of stumbles within the portfolio equals the sum of the imaginary variables that represent the default for one borrower with a Probability of default: D and the default point: A_d For the value of random assets A .

$$A_d = \Phi^{-1}(d) \quad \text{or} \quad d = \Phi(A_d)$$

Where Φ : Is the standard cumulative normal distribution. For example, with $d=1\%$, the default point is $A_d = \Phi^{-1}(1\%) = -2.33$ and so on. If the standard model of asset value for a single borrower is based on the common factor Z where the common factor is used to represent systemic changes or general factors that affect multiple values in the model or system, helps in understanding the interconnectedness of variables and analyzing how the common factor affects the associated outcomes or phenomena and

assumes the value of the borrower's assets i , Y has the following formula Bessis (2015):
 $Y_i = \rho Z + \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} X_i$ In this case, we consider the constant correlation with the common factor is also the correlation between all dependent variables.³ The common probability of default is $d=5\%$, and the default threshold corresponds to the asset value. $\Phi^{-1}(d) = 1.6449$ other For more than one borrower, y : a variable that follows the normal distribution, calculated by the association of P with Z :

$y = \rho \Phi^{-1}(U_1) + \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} \Phi^{-1}(U_2)$ where $u_1 = 0.5$ $Z = \Phi^{-1}(U_1) = 0$
and U_2 : It is an intermediate variable.

We can summarize the simulation process according to the following steps: **First**, Derive the value of the assets. **Second**, the variable y_i is compared to The default threshold where the default occurs when the value of the asset reaches the default point. It goes on to compare the value of the asset to the default point to derive the default variable of the default from the value of the asset, which is equal to 1 when the value of the asset is less or equal to the default point and equal to 0 if the value of the asset is greater than the default point. **Third**, Determine the distribution of alpha and beta in this step the default values are studied based on the coefficients of alpha and beta using the coefficient of beta the default values are converted to a dependent variable following a normal distribution, where the beta distribution is limited by upper and lower limits ranging from zero to one. This means that the resulting beta distribution falls between these two values and that the form coefficients (alpha) and (beta): determine the form of the beta distribution. The alpha coefficient affects the shape of the top and the distribution in the right part of the chart, while the beta coefficient affects the shape of the top and the distribution in the left part of the chart. **Fourth**, Recovery values that follow the beta distribution are converted to a dependent variable that follows a normal distribution, which is explicitly defined as follows Servies (2002):

$$\text{Dependent Variable } = y_i = N^{-1} [\text{Betadist}(\text{RecovRt}_i, \alpha_d, \beta_d, \text{Min}, \text{Max}_d)]$$

$$\text{RecovRT}_i = \min(\text{Max} - \varepsilon, \text{observed recovdry rate}) \quad \varepsilon = \text{some small value}$$

$$\alpha_d = \text{The Beta Distribution's center parameter}$$

$$\beta_d = \text{The Beta Distribution's shape parameter}$$

$$\text{Min} = \text{Set to zero for all cases}$$

$$\text{Max}_d = \text{Set to 1.1 for bonds, but otherwise is 1.0}$$

$$d = \{\text{loans, bonds, preferred stock}\}$$

"d" corresponds to each type of debt. Distributions of three different asset classes can be calculated by specifying two values for the alpha and beta form coefficient. For each beta distribution, many of these distributions can be captured, and it is possible, through the algebraic coefficient, to determine the beta distribution that simply corresponds to the mean and the mathematical standard deviation, as the beta

³ $\text{Cov}(Y_i, Y_j) = \text{Cov}\{\rho Z + \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} X_i, \rho Z + \sqrt{1 - \rho^2} X_j\} = \rho^2 \Phi^2 + \text{Cov}((X_i, X_j))$

⁴ Since U_1 represents the cumulative probability of a standard normal random variable, the value 0.5 corresponds to the arithmetic mean 0 of the standard normal random variable.

distribution is a function of the gamma distributions when the minimum is set to zero, the distribution can be described as follows.

$$\text{beta}(x, \alpha, \beta, \text{Min}= 0, \text{Max}) = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+\beta)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \left[\frac{x}{\text{Max}} \right]^{\alpha-1} \left[1 - \frac{x}{\text{Max}} \right]^{\beta-1} \left[\frac{1}{\text{Max}} \right] \dots \dots (19)$$

The coefficients of the beta distribution form can be extrapolated in several ways, for example, they can be converted to an average or standard deviation:

$$\alpha = \frac{M}{\text{Max}} \cdot \left[\frac{\mu(\text{Max}-\mu)}{\text{Max}-\sigma^2} - 1 \right] \dots (20) \quad \text{and} \quad \beta = \alpha \cdot \left[\frac{\text{Max}}{\mu} - 1 \right] \dots (21)$$

On the contrary, given the beta distribution parameters, the average and standard deviation can be easily calculated.

$$\mu = \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta} \cdot \text{Max} \dots (22) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha \cdot \beta}{(\alpha + \beta)^2 + (\alpha + \beta)}} \cdot \text{Max} \dots (23)$$

Fifth, Estimating the value at risk: The value at risk is α -quantile, meaning that it divides the data into two parts; if the value α is 0.05, then 0.05-quantile ratio represents the value in which 5% of the data is in the lower tail (the lower part) of the distribution, and therefore 95% of the data in the upper tail (the upper part) of the distribution. Assuming L_i And $i=1,2,\dots,n$ is an independent value for estimating the risk value (simulation output. $\widetilde{L}_n$.

N is the number of attempts, where L_i Statistical commands are indicated in the same sequence but in ascending order.

$$L_{(1)} \leq L_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq L_{(n)} \quad \dots \dots (24) \quad \frac{j}{N} \leq \alpha < \frac{j+1}{N}$$

$L_{(j)}$ Is approximation $(1-\alpha)$ -quantile of the loss distribution.

About the Syrian International Islamic Bank: The Syrian International Islamic Bank was established in the form of an anonymous Syrian joint stock company on 07/09/2006, with a capital of fifteen billion Syrian pounds distributed over 150.000.000 shares worth 100 Syrian pounds per share, and on 02/06/2009 it was listed on the stock market. The bank continued to expand with the opening of branches in the provinces and major cities until the bank branches had 26 branches and offices in various cities SIIB (2014).

The Bank obtained the ISO certificate in 19/11/2015, the Bank prepared to implement the requirements of Basel III after the completion of the application of the requirements plan for compatibility with Basel II, each year, the Bank prepares stress tests on the investment portfolio to study its impact on the allocations to be hedged, based on the directives of the Central Bank of Syria, by preparing the effort tests in a quarterly manner according to previously defined scenarios.

Table 2. Includes information about SIIB (created by the authors).

Number of shares in millions	Capital in 2011 in millions	Date of listing on the stock exchange	Date of direct	Date of establishment	Symb ol	Name of the bank
10	5000	02/06/2009	2007/09/15	2006/09/07	SIIB	Syrian International Islamic Bank

5. Research Methodology and Hypotheses Test:

The study was based on the analytical descriptive approach through reference to many books, references, and scientific journals, both Arab and foreign, and the study also used the case study method through the study of the investment portfolio at the Syrian International Islamic Bank in Aleppo.

The study community is considered one of the main sectors affecting the Syrian economy and is one of the leading Syrian Islamic private banks operating in the Syrian Arab Republic, and the sample of the study was derived from the previous society through the selection of the Syrian International Islamic Bank in Aleppo for the availability of data related to the Islamic portfolio of the branch of Aleppo. For this study, it was first: necessary to determine the probability of stumbling in the investment portfolio of the Syrian International Islamic Bank in Aleppo, where the study was based on the model KMV (the model of the KMV was relied on in the probability of stumbling because it is a model developed from the Merton model. this takes into account the multiple default probability values between 0 and 1 that fit the requirements of the study as well as being a model approved by Basel). By applying relevant relationships to calculate the probability of default:

$$DPT = STD + 0.5 LTD.....(25)$$

Table 3. Involves calculating the expected loss value for each fund in the investment portfolio Based on data from the Islamic Bank's loan portfolio. (created by the authors).

PD	DD	σ_A	T	DPT	STD	μ_A	A_0	Value of funding	N
0.056146093	1.58797414	0.075	1	6750000	6,750,000	23.38%	42,900,000	18,300,000	1
0.01	-26.066	0.522	1	6300000	6,300000	1%	48,870000	24,000000	2
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.00451	0.122583972	0.0154	2	88,250,000	88,250,000	22.6%	798,250,000	49,000,000	3

$$DD = d_2 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{A_0}{DPT}\right) + \left(\mu_A - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_A^2\right)T}{\sigma_A\sqrt{T}} \dots\dots\dots(26)$$

$$PD = N(-DD) \dots\dots(27)$$

Second: after reaching the probability of default PD through the previous step, we must determine the amount of loss resulting from the probability of default for each loan by determining the value of each EAD and LGD and the following equation to calculate the expected loss value for each loan.

$$EL = \mathbb{E}(\widetilde{L}_n) \cdot EAD \cdot PD \cdot LGD$$

To determine the value of $LGD = 1 - RR$ you must calculate the value of both alpha and beta transactions and rely on the table in the appendix by applying the following equations:

$$\alpha = \frac{M}{Max} \cdot \left[\frac{\mu \cdot (Max - \mu)}{Max - \sigma^2} - 1 \right] \dots\dots(28) \quad \text{و} \quad \beta = \alpha \cdot \left[\frac{Max}{\mu} - 1 \right] \dots\dots(29)$$

The default value is defined.. Max as 1 and the value of RR by the following equation: $RR = \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta} \cdot Max$

Table 4. Includes data relating to the calculation of the probability of default Based on data from the Islamic Bank's loan portfolio. (created by the authors):

Third: conducting a Monte Carlo simulation to estimate the maximum loss that can be

EL	EAD	LGD	RR	β	α	M_{ax}	σ	μ	PD	N
516380.95	19489500.00	0.4719	0.5281	112.250	125.618	1	3.23%	53%	0.05614	1
9283700	21590000	0.43	0.57	973.9875	129.0997	1	1.04%	57%	0.01	2
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
123116.07	57820000	0.4719	0.5281	112.25	125.618999	1	3.23%	53%	0.00451	3

experienced by the investment portfolio:

- 1- We generate the random variable $Y_i \sim n(0,1)$ by generating random numbers for each debtor in the wallet where the portion of the granted loan is represented idiosyncratic part to reflect individual differences in behavior or performance.
- 2- We calculate the probability of default and the amount of expected loss corresponding to each loan within the portfolio.
- 3- We perform a simulation of (N) a borrower within the portfolio to obtain the distribution of the expected losses within the portfolio, based on the **R-Studio** program.

Figure3. The graph shows the distribution of losses in the portfolio as a result of the simulation process (from the output of the R-Studio programming language)

Fourth: Forecasting the future value at risk based on the outputs of the Monte Carlo simulation

To estimate the value at risk we assume that L_i And $i=1,2,\dots,n$ are independent values from the simulation output. $\widetilde{L}_n$

N is the number of attempts, where L_i statistical commands are indicated in the same sequence but in ascending order

$$L_{(1)} \leq L_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq L_{(n)}$$

Thus, we obtain the value at risk programmatically through :

$$\frac{j}{N} \leq \alpha < \frac{j+1}{N}$$

Fifth: Hypothesis testing: We will test the null hypothesis against the alternative hypothesis which states that

- **H0:** The maximum expected loss of the credit portfolio at SIIB in Aleppo at the level of confidence of 99% will not exceed the total projected losses of individual loans in the portfolio currently assuming no change in the composition of the portfolio.

The total projected losses for individual loans in the portfolio were 99923197, while the maximum projected loss was 73357338, so we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis.

6. Conclusions:

The results indicate that the value at risk in the future is greater than the sum of the losses expected at the confidence level of 99% and based on the above, the Monte Carlo simulation model allows the predictability of the future value at risk. Syria International Islamic Bank should reduce the size of the loan portfolio in the coming

period to reduce the risk value of the portfolio in the future, and rely on other investment alternatives due to the high risks associated with it, in addition to forming appropriate allocations to meet the potential for large expected losses.

The Islamic Bank of Syria could also consider the possibility of repricing loans according to the new formula and consider the size of the appropriate economic capital to cover these risks.

In theory, this study expands knowledge about how these models are used in different environments, including emerging markets or regions facing special economic conditions, and helps to identify the unique characteristics of local markets or economic conditions in Aleppo. This study highlights the use of quantitative techniques in the identification and prediction of financial risks, which enhances the theoretical understanding of the importance of these techniques in the field of risk management.

This study has several limitations: The difficulty of representing unexpected risks in a region affected by unstable geopolitical or economic factors, such as Aleppo, and there can be unexpected risks that are difficult to model using traditional Monte Carlo simulations. Interpreting the results of a Monte Carlo simulation can also be complex, and it may be difficult for decision-makers to understand how to apply the results to practical decisions, especially if they have limited knowledge of quantitative modeling and risk management.

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- List of shape labels:

Figure1.Distribution of the value of the company's assets when the loan is due Zieliński (2009).

Figure2.Distribution of investment portfolio loss variables. Leeuwarden, (2011).

Figure3.The graph shows the distribution of losses in the portfolio as a result of the simulation process (from the output of the R-Studio programming language)

Appendices

Table 1 - Characteristics of Return on Defaulted Debt (RDD)¹ Observations by Default and Instrument Type* (Moody's Ultimate Recovery Database 1987-2009)

		Bankruptcy			Out-of-Court			Total		
		Count	Average	Standard Error of the Mean	Count	Average	Standard Error of the Mean	Count	Average	Standard Error of the Mean
Bonds	RDD		25.44%	3.75%		44.22%	21.90%		26.44%	3.74%
	LGD at Default ²	837	57.40%	1.07%	47	38.68%	3.47%	884	56.37%	1.04%
	Discounted LGD ³		52.03%	1.26%		30.96%	3.00%		50.84%	1.23%
Loans ⁴	RDD		32.57%	5.71%		26.161%	18.872%		32.21%	5.49%
	LGD at Default ²	485	32.57%	5.71%	29	40.40%	6.17%	514	52.81%	3.23%
	Discounted LGD ³		50.00%	1.68%		38.31%	5.79%		49.34%	2.25%
Total	RDD		28.05%	3.17%		37.33%	15.29%		28.56%	3.11%
	LGD at Default ²	1322	55.98%	0.86%	76	39.32%	3.15%	1398	55.05%	0.84%
	Discounted LGD ³		51.55%	1.03%		33.76%	2.89%		50.58%	0.99%

1 - "Return on Defaulted Debt": annualized simple rate of return on defaulted debt from just after the time of default (1st trading date)
2 - Par minus the price of defaulted debt at the time of default (average 30-45 days after default) as a percent of par.
3 - The ultimate dollar loss-given-default on the defaulted debt instrument = 1 - (total recovery at emergence from bankruptcy or time of final settlement/oustanding at default). Alternatively, this can be expressed as (oustanding at default - total ultimate
* Reproduced from: Jacobs, M., (2009), "An Empirical Study of the Returns on Defaulted Debt and the Discount Rate for Loss-Given-Default", Working Paper, OCC

1. # Number of obligors in the portfolio
2. n <- 100
3. # Given variables
4. alpha <- c(125.618999, 125.618999, 1291.099749)
5. beta <- c(112.2507208, 112.2507208, 973.9875296)
6. PD_values <- c(0.004512183, 0.056146093, 0.01)
7. LGD_values <- c(0.4719, 0.4719, 0.43)
8. EAD_values <- c(57820000.00, 19489500.00, 21590000.00)
9. # Parameters of the beta distribution

```

10. b1 <- alpha[1]
11. b2 <- beta[1]
12. # Replace the existing values with the given variables
13. PD <- rep(PD_values, n)
14. LGD <- rep(LGD_values, n)
15. EAD <- rep(EAD_values, n)
16. lossrealization <- function(n, PD, EAD, LGD, b1, b2) {# Keep track of the
    loss in this portfolio
17. totalloss <- 0
18. # Draw Q
19. Q <- rbeta(1, b1, b2)
20. # Loop through all obligors to see if they
21. # go into default
22. for (obligor in 1:n) {# Does this obligor go into default or not?
23. default <- rbinom(1, 1, PD[obligor])
24. # Check for default
25. if (default == 1) {totalloss <- totalloss + EAD[obligor] * LGD[obligor] }}
26. return(totalloss) }
27. runs <- 10000
28. # Run a number of realizations
29. losses <- numeric(runs)
30. for (run in 1:runs) {# Add a new realization of the loss variable
31. losses[run] <- lossrealization(n, PD, EAD, LGD, b1, b2) }
32. # Calculate the breaks for the histogram
33. breaks <- seq(min(losses), max(losses), length.out = 20)
34. # Plot the histogram with adjusted breaks and without gaps between bars
35. hist(losses, breaks = breaks, freq = FALSE, main = "Histogram of Loss",
36. xlab = "Loss", ylab = "Density", border = FALSE)
37. alpha_level <- 0.99 # Alpha level
38. # Sort losses and select the right value for VaR
39. losses <- sort(losses)
40. j <- floor(alpha_level * runs)
41. var <- losses[j]
42. # Output the VaR with formatting
43. cat("Value at Risk (VaR) at", alpha_level * 100, "% confidence level:\n")
44. cat("VaR:", format(var, scientific = FALSE), "\n", sep = "")

```